

**OPEN EARTH
MONITOR**

D8.4 Summary of Workshop "Open-Earth-Monitor" 2023

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List of Abbreviations

2D	Two dimensional
3D	Three dimensional
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use
AGU	American Geophysical Union
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
ARCO	Analysis-Ready and Cloud-Optimized
ARD	Analysis-Ready Data
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CDSE	Copernicus Data Space Ecosystems
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
COG	Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CNR-IT	National Research Council Italy
DAB	Discovery and Access Broker
DestinE	Destination Earth
DESP	DestinE Core Service Platform
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DGGS	Discrete Global Grid Systems
DGGS.jl	Discrete Global Grid Systems in Julia
DRC	Democratic Republic of Congo
DTE	Digital Twin of the Earth
DTW	Dynamic Time Warping
EC	European Council
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EO	Earth Observation
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre
ERA5	ECMWF Reanalysis v5
ESA	European Space Agency
ESSD	Earth System Science Data
EU	European Union
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
EURAC	Accademia Europea Di Bolzano
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FAPAR	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation
FORCE	Framework for Operational Radiometric Correction for Environmental Monitoring
GCP	Global Carbon Project

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GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GeoTIFF	Geographic Tagged Image File Format
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GLAD	Global Land Analysis and Discovery
GFW	Global Forest Watch
GPP	Gross Primary Productivity
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GTIF	Green Transition Information Factories
GTIF-AT	Green Transition Information Factories demonstrator for Austria
HLS	Harmonized Landsat Sentinel-2
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICESAT-2	Ice, Cloud and land Elevation Satellite-2
INPE	Brazilian National Institute for Space Research
ISO	International Standard Organisation
LCL	Land and Carbon Lab
LDN	Land Degradation Neutrality
MAJA	MACCS ATCOR Joint Algorithm
ML	Machine Learning
MPG	Max Planck Institute for biogeochemistry
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
nRMSE	normalized Root Mean Square Error
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NGOs	Non-governmental Organizations
NICFI	Norway's International Climate and Forests Initiative
OEMC	Open-Earth-Monitor Cyberinfrastructure
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGH	OpenGeoHub
OLM	OpenLandMap
OWS	OGC Web Services
PRODES	Programa Despoluição de Bacias Hidrográficas, or "Basin Restoration Program
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System
RECCAP-2	Regional Carbon Cycle Assessment and Processes Phase 2
REDD+	Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation plus
RQA	Recurrence Quantification Analysis
RSQ	R-Squared
S4GF	Space for Green Future
SAF	Satellite Application Facilities
SCL	Scene Classification
SDI	Spatial data infrastructure
SIF	Sun-induced Chlorophyll Fluorescence

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SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SMOS	Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity
SWG	Standard Working Group
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TROPOMI	Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument
TWDTW	Time-Weighted Dynamic Time Warping
U-Net	U-shaped, symmetric convolutional network
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNCCD	UN Convention to Combat Desertification
USA	United States of America
USGS	United States Geological Survey)
VOD	Vegetation Optical Depth
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service
WRI	World Resources Institute
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

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Executive Summary

The first edition of the Open-Earth-Monitor Global Workshop “Connecting open EO solutions to boost European and global goals” took place between 4th and 6th October, 2023 in Bolzano, Italy. With more than 150 participants from organizations pertaining to several EU research institutions, EU agencies, members of the industry and academics; the event reunited some of the most renowned scientists and stakeholders across Europe and the world in the EO field.

During the three-day event, a total of 9 keynote speakers, 23 oral talk presenters and 15 workshop speakers discussed a variety of topics ranging from EO data modelling, geospatial information, digital twins, and land cover monitoring to EO data, technologies and products that might contribute to the EU Green Deal framework.

Other activities included the presentation of the winners of the first two hackathons from the OEMC project: EU Land Cover Classification and Global FAPAR, where a team of young researchers from the hosting partner, EURAC, explained in detail their approach to the 15-day challenge. Similarly, a young student from Turkey, presented the winning solution to the regression problem that the FAPAR challenge entailed. As of the poster presentations, Daniel Loos, from the Max Planck Institute was chosen as the best poster presenter with the work “DGGS.jl. Towards global equal area convolutions using Discrete Global Grid Systems in Julia”.

In summary, this document provides an overview of some of the most relevant presentations in regards the aforementioned topics but also points out the main takeaways that connect the general mission and aims of the OEMC project with the valuable insights shared by the community of stakeholders that gathered in this first edition. Moreover, this document aims at serving as a roadmap for the upcoming editions and stresses the importance of networking, knowledge transfer and collaboration among the interested parties.

Presentation Highlights

#1 Open Earth Observation - Shaping the future by understanding the past (Julia Wageman, independent consultant)

In her presentation, Julia Wageman identified key moments in Earth observation, starting from the open availability of Landsat data, first in 2006 by Brazil for South America and then in 2008 by USGS for the whole globe. Since then, the volume, velocity and variety of open EO data have increased exponentially. This leads to three key trends: a) diversification of users; b) emergence of cloud-based services; c) growing demand for capacity-building.

Julia then described her research which has been focused on user diversification. In her first work ("Users of open big Earth data", Computers and Geosciences, 2021), she found out that the top 5 challenges that are related to finding, accessing, and interoperating big Earth data are: a) limited processing capacity; b) growing data volume; c) lack of standards for dissemination; d) Proliferation of data portals; e) Limited capacity of data discovery.

Julia also discussed the challenges of reproducibility, related to her paper "Five guiding principles to make Jupyter notebooks fit for EO data education" (Remote Sensing, 2022). Her findings and that of other researchers indicate that, although Jupyter notebooks are widely used for sharing scientific results, only 25% of more than 1 million notebooks could be actually executed.

She pointed out the pitfalls of a fragmented data landscape of providers and services, which poses challenges to users to construe. Despite such large availability, Julia's 2021 user survey indicated that data download was still the prevailing mode of data access for 70% of users, while cloud services were accessed by 39% of users, followed by 33% of web services. Note that multiple answers were allowed.

In a later survey (published in "A user perspective on future cloud-based services for big Earth data", Journal Digital Earth, 2021), Julia found out that 70% of users were interested in cloud services. She also discovered that, as of 2011, users in the USA and Canada had more access to cloud services than in Europe, but European experts also had much interest in improving their cloud-based access. Another challenge for prospective cloud users was their lack of capacity to estimate the technical requirements for data storage and processing in the cloud.

Julia concluded her presentation by arguing that the future landscape of EO data and applications will be even more diversified, with the emergence of large-scale AI-based applications. Despite the many technical challenges faced by the EO community to use large-scale EO cloud services, a bigger problem faced by institutions are the so-called "adaptive challenges", which are related to institutional arrangements. Current institutions are not ready to make immediate use of the possibilities allowed by big EO data. These institutions will need to

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be reorganized to benefit from the age of big EO data and build teams of data scientists and thus make a major investment in capacity development.

#2 Earth Observation Open Science and Innovation (Anca Anghlea, ESA)

Anca introduced ways in which Open Science and Innovation are addressed in ESA's Earth Observation Programme, and how such principles are transferred into R&D and Scientific activities. The presentation presented the outlook for ESA's Earth observation missions, that include the Copernicus, Science, and Meteorological missions. The role of Earth Explorer satellites as pathfinder missions to complement the operational aims of the Copernicus program was highlighted.

Anca further presented some important advances of combining open data from different space instruments and in-situ data. Scientists are using data from ESA's Cryosat satellite together with in-situ data to find out spots where the Antarctic ice-sheet is thinning. They observed that 75% of Antarctic ice loss is from the Thwaites and Pine Island Glaciers. Another key part of ESA's EO programme is its Digital Twin Earth, which is the agency's contribution to EC's Destination Earth initiative.

Another discussion point by Anca was about how to open the EO research process. She showed that ESA has been involved with EO Open Science since 2015 and that the initial strategy involved general support for initiatives such as on-line virtual laboratories, open access publications, and open source technologies. She argued that such fragmented investment led to positive results, but failed short of delivering the ultimate goal of opening up EO research. For this reason, ESA is aiming for a more results-oriented approach. This new strategy aims to connect open data, open source, linked to executable code and data, open access, and reproducibility. She highlighted that large-scale adoption requires reproducible results which are understandable and adopted by the EO community.

ESA is looking at similar initiatives such as EU Open Science Policy, UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, and NASA Open Source Science. ESA expects to gain value by advancing Science, improving the trust in Science and innovation, reaching the wider society. Open Science should also foster commercialization, by reducing the development cycle and making cutting-edge solutions available to SMEs.

In conclusion, ESA is working to produce a new EO Science Strategy that will be focused on Open Science and will be published in 2024.

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#3 GEOSS Platform Plus: European efforts to reinforce the use of Earth Observations globally (Alessandro Scremin, Rhea in support ESA)

The presentation described the latest developments in the GEOSS Platform, which is an European-funded project to support GEO (Group on Earth Observations). EC has been supporting GEO since 2005 in implementing GEOSS (Global Earth Observation System of Systems). The aim of the GEOSS Platform is to connect data providers of EO data with the user community. To that end, GEO has engaged with different user communities and regional initiatives to promote the use of open EO data.

Alessandro reported the current challenges of the GEOSS Platform. It only provides data discovery and access, lacking resources such as services, code, documents, and tools. It is also based on an obsolete *discovery-download-processing* paradigm, which is not suitable for big datasets. He also highlighted the opportunities to improve the platform to provide discovery of services, tools and models; the platform should also provide semantic links to enable reproducibility of EO applications.

The new GEOSS Platform being built with European support will build on the existing services to include a community portal and access to virtual labs. The current project is building new tools to support this vision. Such efforts include better support for user registration, and the creation of communities. It will also include improvements in the GEO Discovery and Access Broker (DAB). In addition, links to virtual labs will be provided.

The new GEOSS Portal will have increased emphasis in supporting the open source paradigm. To that extent, it will include tools that enhance the transformation from data to knowledge.

#4 Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem ([Jędrzej Bojanowski](#), CloudFerro)

This presentation by Jędrzej covered the current implementation of the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystems (CDSE), the new initiative supported by EC and ESA to host Copernicus data, application and services. All Copernicus data will be available online - global coverage and the entire time range including the archive - at no cost, for any user. The product list includes Copernicus satellite imagery (Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, Sentinel-5p), Copernicus Services and other satellite data missions (e.g. Landsat, SMOS, Envisat). Moreover, CDSE will offer access to commercial satellite data. Over 40 PB of Copernicus data will be immediately available with a significant daily increase.

Users can download data from CDSE using interfaces such as SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) or the Sentinel Hub software. The CDSE will provide Jupyter Hub as a tool for prototyping, developing, and testing applications for Earth Observation data processing. An openEO interface will also be available to users. These capabilities are available free-of-charge. For those interested in larger scale processing, virtual machines are available on commercial

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terms. Additional third-party providers are joining CDSE to offer a variety of services (both free and commercial).

CDSE will also offer on-demand processing. For Sentinel-1, users can request terrain-corrected backscatter and interferograms. For Sentinel-2, additional processors include a resolution enhancer application, and MAJA and FORCE atmospheric correction and cloud detection.

User environments include a non-cost Jupyter Hub which is integrated with APIs such as openEO, SentinelHub and STAC. User will also have access to commercial services, including virtual machines with GPUs, dedicated servers and containers. They will be able to use Kubernetes technology for building dedicated solutions. Thus, the CDSE will include both public and commercial offerings, the latter to be managed by CREODIAS.

#5 European platforms to support the Green Deal (Benjamin Schumacher, EODC)

Benjamin presented on the capabilities available at EODC (Earth Observation Data Centre), which is linked to the Technical University of Vienna. EODC provides access to a global Copernicus Sentinel Long Term Archive. Its cloud computing platform is connected to powerful processing engines. Through dedicated services, partners and customers can access Teraflops of computational power in EODC. EODC also contributes to the Copernicus Climate Change Services, Copernicus Global Land Services and Global Flood Monitoring Services.

The presentation described components of EODC infrastructure, including the openEO Platform, ESA GTIF Austria, STAC, and Pangeo. The openEO Platform provides standardized and open interfaces for accessing and processing Earth Observation (EO) data. By fostering collaboration and interoperability, openEO supports the development of innovative applications and services. The STAC standardizes the organization and discovery of geospatial assets, making it easier to find and use EO data. Pangeo, an open-source platform for scalable Earth science, empowers researchers with tools and resources for analyzing massive climate and environmental datasets. By offering Jupyter notebooks, cloud computing, and data catalogs, Pangeo facilitates collaborative research and data-driven decision-making.

Benjamin also presented EODC's vision of the Green Deal Data Space, which would be a federation of data ecosystems enabling policy makers, researchers and citizens from Europe to jointly work to address Climate Change.

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#6 Global Analysis-Ready and Cloud-Optimized (ARCO) Landsat Mosaics: Challenges and implementation strategies (Leandro Parente, OGH)

This presentation described the efforts ongoing at OpenGeoHub (OGH) to provide a global set of analysis-ready data (ARD) for the various satellites of the Landsat program. OGH is developing a workflow to produce analysis-ready and cloud-optimized (ARCO) global mosaics including:

1. data harmonization,
2. cloud and artifact screening,
3. temporal aggregation,
4. gapfilling and
5. Mosaicking.

Relying on de-facto standards (Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF - COG and SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog - STAC), the Landsat global ARCO mosaics have potential to boost the access of Landsat data and contribute with the monitoring of land use conversion, food production, biodiversity, climate change and land productivity.

The work by OGH combines the data provided by GLAD (Global Land Analysis and Discovery) by University of Maryland which provides a-sixteen-day composites using Landsat-5, Landsat-7 and Landsat-8 satellites. Based on GLAD data, OGH is producing a 2-month composite with gap-filling to account for cloudy pixels. The remaining gaps are filled considering a temporal weighting filter that builds a gap-filled image where time series for each pixel are reconstructed. The convolution filter for reconstruction can be tuned to respect to causality and seasonality.

OGH created a benchmark data set ("A harmonized Landsat Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset for benchmarking time series reconstruction methods of vegetation indices¹" based on the harmonized Landsat Sentinel-2 (HLS) collection where the artificial gaps are introduced with a realistic spatio-temporal distribution. The data set contains six tiles representative of the main climate classes (e.g. equatorial, arid, warm temperature, boreal and polar).

Moreover, OGH is implementing a STAC endpoint to provide access to the ARCO dataset and other data sets produced by the organization (<http://stac.openlandmap.org>). OGH intends to use toolkits such as *scikit-map* in Python and *sits* in R to run machine learning algorithms in the ARCO dataset.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8119407>

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#7 Monitoring the Earth System with xcube (Gunnar Brandt, Brockmann Consult)

This presentation described the xcube open-source Python package, which offers a suite of tools for transforming EO data sets into analysis-ready data cubes. It integrates into Python's data science stack, and extends PangEO by providing specific data stores for the access to relevant datasets for Earth System Science and tools for data provisioning and exploitation.

The xcube software allows the creation of data cubes from heterogeneous data sources and data with gaps and noisy pixels. These cubes can be published in the cloud, enabling users to access and utilize the data more efficiently. As an open-source Python package, xCube is capable of managing and analyzing vast amounts of data in an efficient and user-friendly manner.

The xcube provides a unified data access to multiple data stores, which include ESA CCI, Climate Data Store, Copernicus Marine Service, and Sentinel Hub. Currently, Brockmann Consult is improving xcube to include detailed information in the associated metadata. The company provides a lightweight xcube server that supports S3 API and OWS WMTS. The xcube viewer is a web-based viewer that connects to xcube datasets and allows on-the-fly execution of user code.

The xcube API provides high-level functionalities for data cubes, including: access, extraction, resampling, masking, chunking, and storage. The development roadmap includes addition of computation functions, alignment to openEO, and support for dask-cluster back-ends.

#8 Reproducible and Reusable Remote Sensing Workflows (Edzer Pebesma, University of Münster)

This workshop laid emphasis on the current status and future strategies for reproducibility in the field of Remote Sensing. The first part of the workshop provided short contributions about recent activities that facilitate reproducible Remote Sensing today. In the second part, participants were engaged to formulate a vision or roadmap on how reproducibility should look when working towards FAIR and open data science.

Edzer discussed the idea and challenges of establishing an independent Journal for Reproducible Remote Sensing. Some of the challenges include:

- A. how to deal with large datasets?
- B. how to include software that cannot be shared (including commercial software and HPC models?)
- C. how to find code reviewers that assert quality and give feedback?

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Edzer further elaborated the motivation for openEO was fuelled by the need to compare cloud-based platforms. The ability to run openEO back-ends locally helps development and code check. He pointed out that it is hard to describe and share openEO process graphs and raised the question as to whether one should share openEO process graphs or Jupyter notebooks with openEO based-scripts in Python, Julia or R.

Progressively, Anca Anglhea discussed the emphasis placed by ESA on reproducible workflows. ESA is considering the use of openEO process graphs and OGC Application Packages. ESA is also discussing with ESSD and AGU on how to provide scientists with means and incentives to publish their data and code.

Edzer Pebesma stated that reviewing EO scripts is hard work, because high-level Python and R scripts rely on third-party packages which are hard for a reviewer to verify their correctness. He stated "*there is little certification in Earth observation*".

The conclusion of the workshop is that the emergence of big data and cloud computing has increased the challenges for reproducibility and reusability in Earth observation. Such recognition should not deter scientists and experts from continuing to pursue such worthy goals.

#9 DestinE Core Service Platform (Inés Morère, ESA)

This talk described the DestinE (Destination Earth) Core Service Platform that will operate an open ecosystem of services to support DestinE-data exploitation and information sharing. DestinE is a flagship initiative of the European Commission, implemented by ESA, ECMWF, and EUMETSAT. Its aim is to develop a digital model of the Earth to monitor, simulate and predict the interaction between natural phenomena and human activities. It will support policies for adaptation and mitigation of Climate Change.

Its contribution to researchers and scientists will be to provide access to EO, model outputs and socio-economic data. It aims to create a development ecosystem to develop, share and optimize Earth-related models. Phase 1 (2022-2024) of DestinE Core Service Platform will lead to the integration of routine services while phase 2 (2024-onwards) will lead to enhanced applications and collaborative environments.

While ECMWF is in charge of the Digital Twin Engine, EUMETSAT will host a data lake, and ESA will be responsible for the DestinE Core Service Platform (DESP). DESP includes key essential services such as:

- user management service,
- infrastructure as a service with storage, network, and CPU/GPU capabilities,
- data access and retrieval service, in particular from the DestinE Data Lake operated by EUMETSAT, as it is the backbone for the data generated by the ECMWF's Digital Twin Engine

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- data traceability and harmonization services,
- basic software suite service for local data exploitation,
- data and software catalog services, and
- 2D/3D data visualization service.

DESP additionally provides onboarding support for integrating external services and resources, making the ecosystem flexible, scalable, and easily adapted to the community needs. DestinE ecosystem aims to support the needs of a large and diverse community of users including general citizens, scientists and academics, commercial entities, or policy makers. DESP Framework defines the required conditions for a service to be part of the ecosystem, and therefore benefit from the available resources, and of the potential to engage with all DestinE users.

#10 Analysis-Ready Data (Peter Strobl, JRC)

This talk presented a fresh perspective on analysis-ready data (ARD). Peter provided an overview of the development of CEOS-ARD and an outlook on the upcoming work in the ISO/OGC SWG. It highlighted the challenges data interoperability poses within and beyond the current 'ARD' framework.

According to the presenter, the popularity of the concept and the expectation for the ARD 'label' in terms of simplified usability and interoperability of a wealth of EO data has spurred the desire to expand ARD beyond classical EO parameters by including higher level products and to cover geospatial data more generically. This has prompted a discussion on which categories, levels, or classes of analysis ready data are needed and how they could be defined and distinguished. These considerations are now taken up by a formal ISO/OGC Standard Working Group (SWG) that was launched recently.

Peter argued that the amount of available geospatial data has increased exponentially and that many of these are available free and open and also calling themselves 'ARD'. However, users relying on their interoperability are often overwhelmed by their diversity and outstanding inconsistencies which often require considerable effort before appropriate data can be selected and joined sensibly. Access to proper reference data and benchmarking methods is therefore an important factor for leveraging 'ARD' in the future.

The presentation reported on some recent efforts to address these through combining top-down international collaboration and bottom-up community efforts. Peter also discussed limitations and obstacles which remain in the way of enabling widespread readiness and interoperability of geospatial data.

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#11 Towards a better estimation of GPP for greenhouse gas accounting through the combined use of SIF, spherical grids and knowledge-guided AI (Greg Duvellier, Max Planck Institute for biogeochemistry)

In his talk, Greg described the challenges in improving the estimates of the land sink, which is one of the most uncertain parts of the Earth's carbon budget. His work is taken in supporting the work of the Global Carbon Project, and more specifically the RECCAP-2 initiative, which needs a proxy for biogenic CO₂ fluxes for the land. These fluxes are associated with the variation of gross primary productivity (GPP) in the Earth's land areas.

Greg described how GPP is determined, including the importance of sun-induced chlorophyll fluorescence (SIF), which is emitted by plants during the photosynthesis process. The SIF signal can be captured by space sensors. Research results indicate there is a non-linear relationship between SIF and GPP, which is hard to establish using only SIF observations. Furthermore, the relation between SIF and GPP changes with stress.

The talk proceeded to describe some recent research results for the estimation of gross primary productivity (GPP) of vegetation using SIF. The SIF signals are impacted by vegetation optical depth (VOD), which is related to how water content is distributed within a canopy, which itself is informative on forest biomass and structure.

Within the OEMC project, Greg and his team at MPG are developing an EO spatial downscaling framework to improve carbon flux estimations using SIF. The spatial downscaling employs EO-derived variables to achieve high resolution estimates. It combines process-based models with knowledge-guided AI.

The use case within OEMC is to develop SIF-based 1km spatial resolution GPP flux estimations based on measurements from the TROPOMI sensor on Sentinel-5P, which has a spatial resolution of about 5 km. The main stakeholder for this product will be the Global Carbon Project (GCP) which aims to establish the greenhouse gas (GHG) budgets of large regions covering the entire globe at the scale of continents. Likewise, Greg detailed the steps required for achieving these goals.

This work also involved the development of a new type of spatial reference system, the DGGS (discrete global grid system). DGGS is made of a hierarchy of uniquely identifiable grid cells that span the globe at multiple resolutions. The MPG team is developing a Julia package to work with DGGS. The advantage of DGGS is using a hexagonal data structure where all cells have equal area and equidistant pixels.

Another component of the MPG approach is the inclusion of machine learning as part of Earth System Science modeling (cf. *Reichstein et al. (2019). Deep learning and process understanding for data-driven Earth system science. Nature, 566(7743), 195–204*). A relevant

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trend is the development of hybrid models, where deep learning is used to improve the ad-hoc parametrization used in many Earth system science models.

#12 Mapping land potential and tracking land degradation using EO data (Julia Hackländer, OGH)

This presentation put forward the on-going work at OGH to use EO data to support the Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) initiative of the UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD). Given that many land areas on Earth are increasingly degrading, this work aims to provide robust monitoring approaches to identify land degradation processes.

The approach taken in this project is to estimate land primary production, one of the key indicators for determining impacts of land degradation. Primary production can be approximated by FAPAR, the fraction of absorbed photosynthetic active radiation, a metric directly related to primary productivity. FAPAR can be measured from space at a coarse resolution.

Julia described a novel methodology to assess land degradation in reference to its natural potential. Using a machine learning model approach, global time series maps spanning 2000 - 2022 have been produced by simulating potential natural FAPAR in the hypothetical space of minimal human impact.

This allows the performance of gap analyses of actual and potential natural FAPAR to monitor impacts of land degradation and restoration efforts through time. Use-case scenarios on country level and project investment level can then help UNCCD in assessing land degradation neutrality (LDN).

#13 Build and visualize your own raster data cube (Leandro Parente, OGH)

Raster data cube is a four-dimensional array with dimensions x (longitude / easting), y (latitude / northing), time, and bands sharing a:

- single spatial reference system,
- constant spatial cell size,
- constant temporal duration,
- temporal reference defined by a simple start and end date / time.

This resulted in a single attribute value for every dimension combination. Building a data cube consists basically in converting raw irregular raster data into a regular and dense structure, which may include information loss and needs to consider user definitions and application restrictions.

In this session, Leandro presented tools that allow experts to access image collections using SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs (STAC), build a custom raster data cube and publish it as Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG). Leandro also showed how to access raster data cubes using QGIS

and through a customized WebGIS solution. The workflow is implemented in Python using pystac, stackstac, eumap and leafmap.

#14 Machine learning ensembles for scalable crop yield modeling (Patric Brandt, Julius Kühn Institute)

This presentation described the use of Copernicus earth observation (EO) data for estimating crop yields. The importance of using EO data for yield data stems from the fact that collecting yield data relies heavily on extensive and time-consuming farm surveys and on-farm measurements.

Patric presented a model-based approach to estimate yields of multiple major crops cultivated in Germany, by employing ML ensembles, using a cloud-integrated spatial data infrastructure (SDI). The model-based yield estimation approach integrates a number of dynamic and static predictors. Analysis ready data of multi-spectral Sentinel-2 imagery is used for space-borne retrieval of crop traits such as leaf area index and above ground biomass. Geospatial data on meteorological time-series are queried from our data cube, providing daily variables such as temperature, precipitation, and global radiation. External geospatial data on soil moisture and physicochemical soil properties are obtained from the Copernicus Global Land Service and SoilGrids 2.0 data portals, respectively. Crop-specific ML models are trained on multi-annual data (2018 - 2022) collected at agricultural parcel level for three crops, i.e. winter wheat, winter barley, and winter rape.

The model employs an ensemble of ML regressors including Gradient boosting, LightGBM, Partial Least Squares, RandomForest, and Support Vector Machines. RSQ values of best performing models inferred from cross validations at parcel level range between 0.67 and 0.74. Related normalized RMSE (nRMSE) values range between 12 and 19%. Aggregated yield estimates at district level compared against mean yields at district level obtained from official yield statistics for 2020 and 2021 show RSQ values for best performing models, ranging between 0.57 and 0.85. Related nRMSE values range between 5–10%. Preliminary results are promising, suggesting several advantages compared to traditional yield estimation approaches, regarding area coverage, cost effectiveness, and timeliness.

#15 Towards a large-scale tool for estimating potential land-cover impacts from Remote Sensing (Daniel E. Pabon-Moreno, MPG)

This talk introduced some preliminary results on the effect of land cover change on climate variables for Europe and Africa. To develop the studies, we created a space-time analytical tool in Julia which estimates the average change of local climate for land cover transition areas. For example, since savannas are usually hotter than neighboring forest, contrasting the local climate conditions can enable one to evaluate the potential effect of the transition from forest to savannas.

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The spatio-temporal analysis tool developed by Daniel includes: a) the space for time technique (Duveiller et al., 2018) which estimates the average change of local climate if the land cover changes from one class to another; b) spatio-temporal cross validation (Meyer et al., 2018); c) forward feature selection (Meyer et al., 2018).

#16 OpenEO in action: How to get started with openEO (Peter Zellner, Michele Claus, EURAC)

openEO is an open API to connect R, Python, JavaScript and other clients to big Earth observation cloud back-ends in a simple and unified way. This workshop illustrated how to use openEO by demonstrating a workflow which includes: login to an openEO Platform, data and process discovery, building process graph, data processing, and visualization. This demonstration revealed the usage and capabilities of the main clients: the Web Editor, the Python Client and the R-Client.

The Web Editor is a webtool to interactively build processing chains by connecting the openEO processes visually. The Python Client and the R-Client are the openEO Platform entry point for programmers. They facilitate the interaction with the openEO API within the respective programming languages and integrate the advantages of the available geospatial packages and typical IDEs.

The demonstration used the Python Jupyter notebook available in the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE). It showed how to connect to an openEO backend available at CDSE. It advanced to elaborate the ways to discover the collections available at CDSE and how to load a collection, build a data cube from Sentinel-2 images using bands B03, B11 and the cloud band SCL. These bands are used to define a normalized snow index.

#17 Building a Digital Twin Earth for the Water Cycle: State of the Art and Challenges (Luca Brocca, CNR-IT)

This workshop displayed the Digital Twin of the Earth (DTE) for the water cycle, which is part of the Digital Twin program led by ESA. The Digital Twin solution aims to provide digital replicas to monitor and simulate Earth processes with unprecedented spatial-temporal resolution including the human component. The workshop presents the state of the art of the technologies of Earth observation and Earth System Science and highlights challenges to improve them as part of the Digital Twin initiative.

Luca presented the state-of-the-art of the estimation of the terrestrial water cycle. He argues there are significant differences between moisture maps derived from EO data and those produced by climate models. He compared the surface soil moisture maps for 2022 for Europe produced by EUMETSAT (SAF) with the one derived from ERA5 climate data, which showed significant differences. He also discussed the current trend for producing hydrological maps at

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high-resolution (1 km x 1 km). Luca compared two maps of soil moisture analysis which nominally are tagged as being high-resolution. He argued that many of these maps are unreliable and contain spurious noise; others are produced with downscaling methods which do not capture local variation. Recent soil moisture maps which claim to provide a 30 m x 30 m resolution are in fact produced by downscaling low-resolution maps and combining them with a higher resolution digital elevation model.

Luca went on to show the large variation of hydrological data produced currently. Some data is derived from EO data only; other data sets come from models and some others use a combination of EO and models. This variation leads to many data sets which are not consistent with each other, leading to lack of reliable sources from where end-user products could be derived.

Given these challenges, Luca argued that reliable products can only be built by a collaboration effort of committed experts. Such products are complex to generate and dependent on in-situ data availability. He leads a consortium of institutions which are producing a flood-forecasting model for the Po river in Italy; his experience shows that managing complexity is required to generate good quality products. When one has a good quality product, it is possible to develop "what-if" scenarios for water resources management.

#18 OpenLandMap: Global ARCO environmental layers (Tom Hengl, OGH)

Tom exhibited the OpenLandMap (OLM), an open data system providing data and services to help produce and share data sets on the actual and potential status of multiple environmental variables. The layers of OLM include soil properties/classes, relief, geology, land cover/use/degradation, climate, current and potential vegetation. OpenLandMap is accessible by a web-mapping interface. The aim of OpenLandMap is to become an Open Street Map-type system for land data. OpenLandMap data is based on the concept of ARCO ("Analysis-Ready Cloud Optimised") data.

OpenGeoHub currently hosts 15 TB of data including 1 km daily and monthly climatic products (min, max temperature and precipitation), potential natural vegetation, 250 m MODIS products, 100 m land cover and land use maps, 100 m maps of soil properties, 30 m land cover maps and digital terrain models. The land cover maps (1992–2018) come from the ESA-CCI initiative. OLM includes the HILDA data set (1 km x 1 km) Global Land Changes (1960-2019). MODIS MCD12Q1 and MOD13Q1 data have been available since 2000. The [OpenLandMap.org](https://www.openlandmap.org) web interface also provides derived EO products, such as the potential distribution of biomes, and potential annual and monthly FAPAR.

Tom also presented the rationale for OpenLandMap (OLM), which is to allow users an integrated access at no cost and also to provide access to both raster and vector environmental data. Relevant vector data sets include lidar and in-situ data. To carry out geospatial data

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manipulation in OLM and in Python in general, the team at OGH developed a software package called scikit-map. This package provides machine learning methods to work with OLM data and geospatial data in general. In terms of data access, OpenLandMap can be queried using the STAC API. Access in QGIS to OLM data is available using COG tiles. Tom also gave an example of comparison of the power of data integration, by showing how well existing DEM data sets match the canopy height data provided by ICESAT-2.

#19 Monitoring deforestation in Amazonia: transitioning from visual interpretation to satellite time series analysis (Gilberto Camara, INPE-Brasil)

This talk discussed the ongoing work at the Brazilian National Institute for Space Research (INPE) to replace highly-accurate visual interpretation of deforestation in Brazilian Amazonia by machine-learning methods that process satellite image time series. INPE makes yearly assessments of deforestation in the Brazilian Amazonia rain forest since 1988, INPE's data is considered authoritative by the scientific community, national and international media, and is used as a basis for Brazil's reporting of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Due to the need for high accuracy of the result, the PRODES maps are produced by visual interpretation and have a 93% accuracy. However, doing visual interpretation of an area of 4 million km² requires substantial human resources. For this reason, INPE is working to transition the current data production technique to a method based on big data analytics using Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-2A images.

The INPE team has developed new methods for producing deforestation and land use and land cover change maps using satellite image time series. The method requires a regular data cube of dense satellite images. Experts provide training samples that represent the possible deforestation events. These samples train machine learning and deep learning classifiers, which work on a time-first, space-later basis. First, each pixel location is associated to a time series that is classified. Then, a neighborhood-based Bayesian smoother is applied to remove outliers and produce results that approximate those of visual interpreters. The resulting maps have a 98% coincidence with those done by human experts.

#20 Global land use and land cover monitoring: From Data to Impact (Lindsey Sloat, WRI)

This talk addressed the work of World Resources Institute's Land and Carbon Lab (LCL). Global land use and land cover monitoring is crucial for understanding and addressing the impacts of land use change on the environment and society. WRI is dedicated to advancing this field through the development of cutting-edge monitoring tools, technologies, and partnerships.

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In her presentation, Lindsay presented important products supported by WRI-LCL for global land use and land cover monitoring and highlighted the ways in which these products are being leveraged to drive positive change. She displayed results in Peru, where WRI is partnering with indigenous communities to protect their lands. A second important product is the association of Global Forest Watch (GFW) data to development banks in Latin America, highlighting areas where bank loans are associated with deforestation and biodiversity loss. In the Congo Basin, GFW data is helping governments improve land use planning.

Based on WRI's experience, Lindsay argued that it is important that the EO community makes an effort to "track their user's stories". Given that EO products are in demand for environmental monitoring, it is important to understand who their users are. Lindsay pointed out some examples of stakeholders. Law enforcement officers, bank portfolio managers, policy-makers, supply-chain compliance officers, legislators, NGOs, indigenous communities and journalists are some examples of users of EO products. Each type of user has specific needs that ought to be considered by those who generate products out of basic EO data.

The presenter also described the evolution of GFW, using the well-known "Gartner technology hype cycle". She argued that GFW has passed the early phases of technology adoption with peaks of inflated expectations and troughs of disillusionment, and has now matured into a technology that has matured into mainstream adoption. She has presented a perspective of what could be achieved with reliable estimates of land use and land cover changes using medium-resolution (10-30 meters) images. Accurate assessment of land change and associated greenhouse emissions and removals would improve nature conservation, landscape restoration and improve accountability of food systems and supply chains.

One relevant innovation being carried out by WRI-LCL is Global Pasture Watch, a project that aims to map and monitor global grasslands and livestock. The project will use time series from 2000 to 2022+ to map grassland extent and management, pasture condition and productivity, livestock density, and animal husbandry related emissions. Global Pasture Watch will help to understand the global land squeeze, improve accounting of AFOLU emissions, and support better planning of livestock production. Global Pasture Watch consists of four major products:

1. Pasture-class annual maps at 30 meter resolution,
2. Livestock density annual maps at 1 km resolution,
3. Short vegetation height annual maps at 30 meter resolution and,
4. Gross primary productivity bi-monthly maps at 30 meter resolution.

#21 The ESA Green Transition Information Factories – using Earth Observation and cloud-based analytics to address the Green Transition information needs (Patrick Griffiths, ESA)

This presentation reintroduced important efforts on-going at ESA to use EO technologies and data to support the European Green Deal. The ESA Space for Green Future (S4GF) accelerator

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will explore new mechanisms to promote the use of space technologies and advanced modeling approaches for scenario investigations on the Green Transition of economy and society. A central element of the S4GF accelerator are the Green Transition Information Factories (GTIF). GTIF takes advantage of Earth Observation (EO) capabilities, geospatial and digital platform technologies, as well as cutting edge analytics to generate actionable knowledge and decision support in the context of the Green Transition.

A first national scale GTIF demonstrator has now been developed for Austria. It addressed the information needs and national priorities for the Green Deal in Austria. The GTIF demonstrator for Austria (GTIF-AT) builds on top of federated European cloud services, providing efficient access to key EO data repositories and rich interdisciplinary datasets. GTIF-AT initially addresses five Green Transition domains:

1. Energy Transition,
2. Mobility Transition,
3. Sustainable Cities,
4. Carbon Accounting, and
5. EO Adaptation Services.

For each of these domains, scientific narratives are provided and elaborated using scrollytelling technologies.

The GTIF interactive tools combine domain specific scientific results with intuitive Graphical User Interfaces and modern frontend technologies. In the GTIF Energy Transition domain, users can interactively investigate the suitability of locations at 10m resolution for the expansion of renewable (wind or solar) energy production. The tools also allow investigating the underlying conflicts e.g., with existing land uses or biodiversity constraints. Satellite based altimetry is used to dynamically monitor the water levels in hydro energy reservoirs to infer the related energy storage potentials. In the sustainable cities' domain, users can investigate the photovoltaic installments on rooftops and assess the suitability in terms of roof geometry and expected energy yields.

Besides, GTIF enables users to inform themselves and interactively investigate the challenges and opportunities related to the Green Transition ambitions. This enables e.g. citizens to engage in the discussion process for the renewable energy expansion or support energy start-ups to develop new services. The GTIF development follows an open science and open-source approach and several new GTIF instances are planned for the next few years, addressing the Green Deal information needs and accelerating the Green Transition.

#22 Mapping the diversity of land use following deforestation across Africa with active learning (Robert Masolele, WUR)

In his talk, Robert presented the first high-resolution (5 m) continental-scale mapping of land use following deforestation in Africa. The input data of class samples collected on Planet-NICFI

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monthly mosaics from 2015 to 2020. The Planet-NICFI 2022 images were used for classification. The reference land use data consisted of 15 land use classes: small-scale cropland, large-scale cropland, pasture, mining, roads, other-land with tree cover, planted forests, coffee, human settlement, tea plantation, palm oil, rubber, cashew, cacao, and water.

The deep learning training and classification method was Attention U-Net, a method originally developed for medical images that has been extended to remote sensing images by many researchers recently. Robert combined deep learning methods with active learning, an interactive process which identifies wrongly-classified areas in the output map, and then collects training data on these target areas to improve map accuracy. Use of active learning techniques resulted in significant improvement of classification accuracy, raising the overall accuracy from 43% in the first round of classification to 84% in the final map.

Robert also analyzed some results in detail. In Ghana, much forest has been replaced by cocoa plantations. In the Ivory Coast and Tanzania, there are also relevant examples where forest has also been replaced by cash crops. He also showed how large-scale croplands have grown in Zambia and how planted forests are replacing natural vegetation in Cameroon and Gabon. He also identified the encroachment of forests by tree plantations in Kenya and coffee plantations that are under tropical forest canopy in Ethiopia. He pointed out the significant growth in large-scale cropland in Angola and the small-scale cropland that has occupied many former forest areas in Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). Combining the data, Robert developed a map of hotspots of land use change in tropical Africa and estimated what has been the main land uses following deforestation from 2001 to 2020.

There are different drivers of forest loss in tropical Africa. In general, small-scale crop-land is the dominant driver of forest loss with hotspots in Madagascar and DRC. In addition, commodity crops such as cacao, oil palm, and rubber are the dominant drivers of forest loss in the humid forests of western and central Africa, forming an "arc of commodity crops" in that region. At the same time, the hotspots for cashew are found to increasingly dominate in the dry forests of both western and south-eastern Africa, while larger hotspots for large-scale croplands were found in Nigeria and Zambia. The increased expansion of cacao, cashew, oil palm, rubber, and large-scale croplands observed in humid and dry forests of western and south-eastern Africa suggests they are vulnerable to future land-use changes by commodity crops, thus creating challenges for achieving the zero deforestation supply chains, support REDD+ initiatives, and towards sustainable development goals.

#23 Forest loss mapping based on Sentinel-1 time series (Felix Cremer, MPG)

This presentation explored the use of Sentinel-1 time series for assessing deforestation in Central Europe from 2018 to 2020. The authors used recurrence quantification analysis (RQA)

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to derive a change metric which takes the order of the time series into account. This approach provides high resolution yearly forest loss maps based on a continuous data stream.

The RQA algorithm works by comparing every time series against itself, to find out the time steps which are similar to each other. The implementation used the YAXArrays package in Julia. Using this method, Felix showed examples of detection of forest loss in Germany.

#24 Overcoming Data Scarcity in Land Use Monitoring with Time-Weighted Dynamic Time Warping (Victor Maus, Univ of Vienna)

Victor presented the machine learning approach called Time-Weighted Dynamic Time Warping (TWDTW) for data-scarce applications. TWDTW is a satellite image time series classification algorithm that uses a Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distance. DTW is a widely used algorithm in various fields, including speech recognition, medicine, industry, and finance, and has shown promising results in land use mapping due to its ability to deal with gaps in time series, robustness to noise, matching time series of different lengths and intervals, and to keep its classification performance on small training sets.

However, DTW has limitations in matching events regardless of when they occur, which can result in out-of-season alignments and misclassifications—for example, aligning a summer crop to a winter one. TWDTW overcomes this limitation by introducing a time weight to match deviation from an expected date in the training set. This temporal constraint improves classification performance by controlling for out-of-season alignments while keeping DTW's flexibility to smaller phenological fluctuations of vegetation.

This presentation further demonstrated the effectiveness of the TWDTW method for land use classification using the open-source R package `dtwSat`. Overall, this machine learning method is suitable for data-scarce regions and can contribute to land use monitoring, supporting the environmental targets proposed by the European Green Deal and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.

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Main Discussion Points from the Workshop

Indeed, the workshop was a success with notable scientists demonstrating the findings from their research including substantial arguments which have made the human mind to become more curious about our environment. Some of the key messages that have emerged from the Workshop include:

1. The open availability of big Earth observation data is allowing innovative and ground-breaking applications, as shown by the presentations of Lindsay Sloat (WRI), Julia Hacklander (OGH), Gilberto Camara (INPE) and Robert Masolele (WUR).
2. As pointed out by Julia Wageman in her presentation, many institutions that use EO data face significant adaptive challenges. Current institutions are not ready to make immediate use of the possibilities allowed by big EO data. They will need to be reorganized to benefit from the age of big EO data.
3. As part of the European Green Deal, the European Commission (EC) and ESA are investing significantly in EO data and products. ESA is investing in Destination Earth service platforms, as described by Inès Morère. Also, Patrick Griffiths from ESA described how ESA's investment in Green Transition Information Factories can provide user-relevant information for the EU Green Deal.
4. The Digital Twin initiative from EC is motivating innovative research in data integration, analysis and modeling to use EO data to improve models in Earth System Science. Luca Brocca presented the state-of-the-art in hydrological modeling and Greg Duvellier showed the latest results on estimation of the carbon sink.
5. The new initiative of the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem is bound to have a significant impact on availability of EO services. The CDSE business model combines a free tier based on Jupyter Hubs for general uses with commercial services which will be user-focused. The main difference between CDSE and other cloud providers such as Google Earth Engine and Microsoft Planetary Computer is its inbuilt strategy to allow value-added service companies to use the platform. Thus, it is expected that CDSE will encourage European SMEs to work on rapid innovation cycles and thus make a relevant difference to the user community.
6. The OEMC project consortium is making significant advances in the development of technologies and new data products to support advances in big EO data analysis. Innovative products include the Open Land Map and the Landsat ARCO data set from OpenGeoHub. New technologies include OpenEO (University of Münster, EURAC), xCube (Brockmann Consult), and SITS (INPE/Brazil).

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7. The workshop also identified challenges on reproducibility and reuse of EO-based applications. One of the key missing parts is the lack of available specialists and protocols for quality assessment of paper submissions or contributed code available in platforms such as GitHub. As stated by Edzer Pebesma, "*there is little certification in Earth observation*".

In short, arguably the most significant message was the reminder by Lindsay Sloat from WRI: "know your users". As she pointed out, each type of user has specific needs that need to be considered by those that generate products out of basic EO data.

Results & Conclusions

The workshop provided a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art on the EO data, models, and technologies. It also indicated how EO can make a significant contribution to the European Green Deal and to the necessary global transition to sustainable development. The breadth of topics presented was matched by the quality of the presentations. Workshop attendees and those that will access the on-line presentation will find much useful information. The workshop also showed that the Open Earth Monitor project is making significant progress in bringing together a unique community of experts committed to Open Data, Open Software and Open Science.

All recordings including the oral talks, keynotes and workshops can be [accessed here](#) and also on the OEMC project website: <https://earthmonitor.org/knowledge-hub/>. The project coordinator is already preparing for the next Global Workshop to be held in Vienna in October 2024.